

**LINGUISTIC PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATING ARTISTIC
WORKS FROM UZBEK TO ENGLISH AS AN EXAMPLE OF
THE NOVEL "ULUGBEK TREASURE" BY ODIL YAKUBOV**

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Abstract: This article discusses the analysis of linguistic and grammatical transformations in the translation from Uzbek to English of "Ulugbek's Treasure" by Odil Yaqubov, one of the masterpieces of Uzbek literature.

Key words: translation, artistic translation, orthographic transformation, punctuation transformation, lexicological transformation, morphological transformation, syntactic transformation.

INTRODUCTION. Linguistics is the study of languages. There are practical and theoretical types of linguistics, and theoretical linguistics studies the structure (grammar) and its meaning (semantics) of the language. Grammar includes the disciplines of morphology (the structure and change of words), syntax (the rules for joining words into phrases and sentences), and phonology (the study of language using abstract sounds). Applied linguistics mainly deals with the practical application of theoretical knowledge learned in linguistics.

Odil Yakubov is a major representative of Uzbek Soviet literature, born in 1926 in the village of Karnok, Turkestan District, Kazakhstan, in

an intellectual family. When the Second World War started, he pretended to be old enough to participate in the war and went to the Japanese front. He was in actual military service from 1945 to 1950. In 1951-1956, he studied at the Central Asian State University (now the National University). Worked as a reporter on Uzbekistan for "Literaturnaya Gazeta", chairman of the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan, editor-in-chief of "Literature and Art of Uzbekistan" newspaper and other responsible positions. Yakubov was awarded the Order of People's Writer of Uzbekistan in 1985. His first work - the short story "Peers" - was published in 1951. "The First Step" (1953), "Two Loves" (1955), a collection of short stories, "The Golden Ring" (1961) describes love as a great, sacred feeling characteristic of a person. In the story "Holy" (1960). The writer's style and path, characteristic of a true writer, were revealed.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY.

"Treasure of Ulugbek" is a novel written by Uzbek writer Odil Yaqubov. The personal life and tragic fate of the Timur ruler and scientist Mirzo Ulugbek are covered in the work. The work is considered Yakubov's best work and one of the most important novels in Uzbek literature. The novel was published for the first time in 1973 in the city of Tashkent in the publishing house of Literature and Art named after Gafur Gulom. It was reprinted more than ten times, including in 1980-1986 (three volumes of Yakubov's selected works) and 1994. The novel has also been translated into several languages. In 1976, the Russian translation of the novel, translated by Yu Surovsev in cooperation with the author, was published in the publishing house "Sovetsky pisatel" in Moscow. This translation was reprinted in Tashkent in 1979 by Gafur Gulom Publishing House of Literature and Art.[4] The Russian translation was also published in 1981 and 1982 by the publishing house "Progress". In addition, the Russian translation was published in Moscow in 1986 as a collection with

Yakubov's stories by "Khudozhestvennaya literatura" publishing house. K. Seydkhanov translated the novel from Russian into Kazakh, the Kazakh translation was published in 1983 in Almaty by "Jazushi" publishing house. In the same year, a translation of the novel from Russian to Hindi was published in the publishing house Raduga in Tashkent. In 1987, the Lithuanian translation of the novel translated from Uzbek by G. Kobeskaite was published in the publishing house "Mintis" in Vilnius.

RESULTS.In conclusion, the purpose of writing this article is to give a little information about the work to those who are taking their first step into the world of books and readers who are not ready to read books, and to provide correct information about the original content of the work to the readers. .

DISCUSSION Semantic Transformation Method: There are many words in this work that can be examples of semantics. For example: if the phrase "**my word**" is translated as "**my word is this**", I was not satisfied with the translation, and after adding another word next to it, that is, depending on the meaning of the preceding sentence, "my "to think queer thoughts", if we directly translate the phrase "to think queer thoughts" as "to feel myself", the meaning of the translation will not appear. , that is, "along with feeling lonely, he also carries strange thoughts in his head ", if we connect it to the words next to it, the translation will be colorful.

Method of lexicological transformation: in this case, many place names are mentioned by individuals, of course, they cannot be written directly in Uzbek language. For example:

1. Kesh
2. Shahrizabz
3. Movarounnahr words are directly adapted to the Uzbek language. If we take place names as an example, Bungalov is a room attached to a castle, and there are many similar analyzes that I will mention during the

translation. As for the above words, in the 1st analysis, I mentioned taking risks, and in the second analysis, not being afraid of risks. The word "perhaps" does not change any meaning. Syntactic transformation method: I put each syntactic symbol in its place without any changes. Even if one exclamation point or hyphen is changed, the content of the entire header text will change. For example, "Common fine bonnet" is considered the main content of this compound sentence, and it means the remains of common people, that is, the original meaning is "common fine bonnet" in translation. Don't let anyone know that you took out the outside. gives the meaning, both in fact and in the correct translation. Panic - stricken, this word underwent a semantic transformation into a syntactic transformation in the translation and created a different meaning in the translation. In the 2nd part of the work, many lexicological and syntactical transformations have taken place. For example "every body goo right!". Many punctuation marks were added when this word was translated into Uzbek. "let's go!" - said Ali Kushchi and shouted "who can help mee"! (-) is added directly when converting from Uzbek to English . We can also see in the above sentence. It is difficult to give many examples of morphological analysis, because it is difficult to analyze the work on the basis of the noun, adjective, and grammar, but examples have been given. For example, "I have expressed my wish I know to breed my tree wealth not but the services" this phrase is translated as surprise of the second day in Uzbek language, but it causes confusion in the translation. Beautiful woman with black eyebrow and eyes a coored nose she had no angel and cold face, it would be appropriate to translate it. Navkar - This word, when translated directly into English, has a general meaning. This novice was cited in the translation.

1. Kuksaray
2. Chin

3. Oksaray

4. When Ali Kushchi translates the names of these persons and places into English, the sounds change and undergo lexicological transformation. The word "don't let him" is 420 in Uzbek, but when translated into English, it became an imperative.

CONCLUSION In this article, the problems encountered in turning into the translation language using lexicological, morphological, syntactic, and transformations in the sentences given in the work selected as the object of translation are considered.

REFERENCES

1. Adil Yakubov. —Treasure of Ulugbek. Nodirabegim publishing house. Tashkent - 2019, page 137.
2. Solizhonov Juraali Kamoljonovich. (2022). Lingua-perspective Problems and Solutions of Translating the Plant and Food Names in the "Harry Potter" books from English into Uzbek. ASEAN Journal on Science & Technology for Development, Vol 39(No 4), 221–229. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6607317 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6607317>
3. Kamoljonovich, SJ (2022). LINGUISTIC-PERSPECTIVE PROBLEMS OF ANTHROPONYM IN JK ROWLING'S FANTASY WORKS. Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS), 2(1), 334-343. <https://doi.org/10.24412/2181-2454-2022-1-334-343>
4. Kamoljonovich, SJ, & O'G, YNUB (2022). ANALYSIS OF TRANSLATION METHODS FOR ARTISTIC TRANSLATION (IN THE EXAMPLE OF THE WORKS OF IAN TUHOVISKY). Educationists, 18(5), 32-37.
5. Jo'ramurodova, Z., & Solijonov, J. (2022, April). THE PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATING ANTHROPONYM FROM UZBEKI TO ENGLISH IN JK ROWLING'S —THE TALES OF BEEDLE THE BARD. In MEJDUNARODNAYA NAUCHNAYA

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PARADIGMY: VZAIMODEYSTVIE TRADITSIY I INNOVATSIY II"
(Vol. 2, No. 18.03, pp. 554- 560).
<https://doi.org/10.47100/nuu.v2i18.03.115>

6. Kadyrovna, AZ, & Kamoljonovich, SJ (2022). A LINGUISTIC
PERSPECTIVE ANALYSIS OF JK ROWLING'S TRANSLATION OF
THE IMAGE OF WIZARDS IN HARRY POTTER AND THE
SORCERER'S STONE FROM ENGLISH TO UZBEKI. Central Asian
Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS), 2(3), 176-180.
<https://doi.org/10.24412/2181-2454-2022-3-176-180>